

GENERAL INFORMATION

FAIR Chemistry Data: A Research Data Management Workshop Concept

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- General_information.docx/.pdf
- Exercises.docx/.pdf
- Example_workshop_pad.md
- README.txt
- Training_concept.xlsx
- NFDI4Chem_MOX.pptx/.pdf (x=1, 2, 3, 4)
- Plain_MOX.pptx/.pdf (x=1,2,3,4)
- Speaker-notes_M01.pdf (x=1,2,3,4)

- M01E01_Example_Mentimeter.pdf
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- M02E03_Import_for_Miro.rtb
- M02E06_Example_Miro.pdf
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- M02E06_Worksheet.docx/.pdf
- M03E01_Example_Miro.pdf
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- M03E02_Example_Pad.md
- M03E02_Group_Pad.md
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Preface

This open educational resource (OER) is based on the workshop 'FAIR Research Data Management: Basics for Chemists', which has been delivered over 40 times to more than 800 participants within the NFDI4Chem framework since 2022. NFDI4Chem is the chemistry consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany. You can find out more about our work on our website¹ and in our published proposals^{2,3}.

The workshop introduces the fundamentals of research data management (RDM) to researchers working in chemistry and related disciplines, and therefore includes many examples specific to chemistry. We demonstrate how good RDM can be applied in practice, highlighting chemistry-specific features and introducing relevant tools and services.

The target group is primarily early career researchers, such as doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers. However, participants in our workshops have ranged from technical assistants and data stewards to other research support staff, (junior) group leaders and professors.

This general information is designed to help you reuse the materials effectively. It outlines the structure of the workshop concept, explains how the slides and exercises can be combined and provides practical recommendations for customisation and implementation. The aim is to provide sustainable and scalable training in research data management (RDM) which allows for maximum flexibility and local adaptation.

The workshop concept package includes a modularised slide deck in both NFDI4Chem and plain designs, including comprehensive speaker notes and additional reading material, an introduction file, a detailed training concept file, a file describing the exercises and several example files in the template folder. Together, these provide conceptual input, RDM knowledge and interactive elements that can be combined, modified or expanded according to specific learning objectives, target groups and the time available. Users are explicitly encouraged to adapt the content, select individual modules, and customise examples or exercises for their own teaching context.

A first basic version of this training material was published in 2023⁴. Since then, the workshop concept has been extended and reworked, and is now published as a fully usable open educational resource. The workshop material 'DMP Writing Made Easy: A Hands-on Workshop for Chemists', published in January 2026 contains parts of this teaching material⁵.

You are welcome to use our material!

Annett, Ann-Christin, Fabian and Benjamin

¹ <https://nfdi4chem.de/>

² Christoph Steinbeck et al. (2020). NFDI4Chem – Towards a National Research Data Infrastructure for Chemistry in Germany. RIO. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.6.e55852>

³ Christoph Steinbeck et al. (2025). Proposal NFDI4Chem 2025-2030 In the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) – Our Vision: All Chemists Publish FAIR Data. RIO. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.11.e177037>

⁴ Ann-Christin Andres et al. (2023). FAIR Research Data Management: Basics for Chemists. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238499>

⁵ Ann-Christin Andres et al. (2026). DMP Writing Made Easy: A Hands-on Workshop for Chemists (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18349878>

General remarks

The general workshop concept and material is based and inspired by several other published and unpublished training materials:

- Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management^{6,7,8}
- Workshop: 'Research Data Management - Make Your Data Count!' by Research Data Management Helpdesk at Friedrich Schiller University Jena
- Workshop: 'Research Data Management' by RWTH Aachen University

We highly recommend checking out the Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management and its extension modules.

The workshop concept also includes a number of exercises for you to run as part of the workshop. All exercises are described in detail in a dedicated exercises file. Some of these exercises have been newly developed, others were already published in 2024 as part of the exercise catalogue '27 FAIR RDM exercises - A (Chemistry-specific) Catalogue'⁹.

If you reuse our workshop concept, make sure to also cite and acknowledge the resources mentioned above.

Any other figures or specific content used are referenced directly on the slides. Please refer to the 'References' section for further details.

⁶ Katarzyna Biernacka et al. (2021). Train-the-Trainer-Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement (Version 4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773203>

⁷ Katarzyna Biernacka et al. (2023). Train-the-Trainer-Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement (Version 5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10122153>

⁸ Katarzyna Biernacka et al. (2024). Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management (Version 5.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13927614>

⁹ Daniela Adele Hausen et al. (2024). 27 FAIR RDM exercises - A (Chemistry-specific) Catalogue. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13353021>

Modules

This workshop concept consists of four different modules:

Module	Content
M01 – Basics of research data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Introduction RDM, trainers and participants● RDM basics (definitions, NFDI & NFDI4Chem, data life cycle, FAIR principles, open science)● Legal framework (basic terms, policies, copyright, licences, data protection)● Data management plan (definition, funder requirements, RDMO)
M02 – Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Documentation (data organisation, 5S method, metadata and standards, MICHI, controlled vocabulary, machine-readable chemical structures, process management)
M03 – Electronic laboratory notebooks	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● ELN (advantages & criteria, barriers, elabFTW, Chemotion ELN, template development)
M04 – Data preservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Data preservation (storage & backup, data versioning, collaborative work & digital tools, archiving)● Publishing data (reasons for data publication, FAIR in detail, options & requirements, repositories, beyond data)● Finding data

Each module takes about three hours, including a 15-minute break. Two formats for delivering this workshop have been proven to work well in the past: One is a two-day format, with modules M01 and M02 running on day one and modules M03 and M04 running on day two. The other is a four-day format, with modules running on four consecutive days. The latter four-session format works best online.

Concept

You can find the workshop concept in the following file: Training_concept.xlsx.

The concept consists of nine worksheets, which are described in more detail below:

Worksheet 'Overview'

This worksheet provides detailed information about the workshop, including general and file information as well as advice on workshop organisation.

Worksheets 'MXX-Schedule'

The 'MXX-Schedule' worksheets refer to the schedules of the various modules. For example, 'M01-Schedule' provides information on the schedule for module M01, 'Basics of Research Data Management'. The columns in these worksheets contain the following information:

Field name	Definition
Start time [hh:mm]	Planned starting times of the different topics in the concept in the format hh:mm. Here the time is set to 0:00, just adjust the time in cell A2 to your starting time. Calculations of the following starting times are based on the information provided in the column Planned duration [hh:mm]
Actual time [hh:mm]	Here you can track the actual time you started with a given topic. This helps you to optimise time management when running the workshop more often.
Planned duration [hh:mm]	Recommended time you should plan for the topic in the concept. Based on the information provided here, the starting times for all other topics are calculated. The information is provided in minutes.
Trainer	Information on who is running the topic
Support	Information on who is supporting the trainer
Session	Name of the session
Topic	Name of the topic within a session
Slide number	Slide number where this topic can be found in the slide decks
Exercises	Information about the exercises carried out on the topic
Comments/Notes	Additional information and notes on running the sessions
Method	Description of the method used for this topic, e.g. presentation, group work, individual work, poll or quiz

Worksheets 'MXX-LO'

The 'MXX-LO' worksheets provide additional information on the learning objectives for each module. For example, 'M01-LO' provides information on the learning objectives for module M01. These learning objectives are based on the 'Learning Objectives Matrix on the Topic of

Research Data Management (RDM)' by Petersen et al.¹⁰. We hope that using the learning objectives will provide you with further information on the goal of each topic. The columns in these worksheets contain the following information:

Field name	Definition
Session	Name of the session
Topic	Name of the topic within a session
LO subject	Learning objective subject from the Learning Objectives Matrix
LO topic	Learning objective topic from the Learning Objectives Matrix
Bloom Level	Learning level of the learning objective taxonomy according to Bloom taken from the Learning Objectives Matrix
Learning Objectives for each module (M01-LO, M02-LO, M03-LO, M04-LO)	Learning objective statement from the Learning Objectives Matrix
Relevant LO-ID	Identifier in the Learning Objectives Matrix, if known

¹⁰ Britta Petersen, et al. (2025). Learning Objectives Matrix on the Topic of Research Data Management (RDM). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15846806>

Master slides

PowerPoint (Version 2510, Build 19328.20158, Microsoft 365) was used for generating this training material. We provide slides with two different designs: NFDI4Chem and plain. The NFDI4Chem design uses the IBM Plex Sans font, which is freely available¹¹. The plain design is based on the Calibri font. The content of the slide decks is identical. Each slide master consists of the following pre-defined slide layouts:

Title	Slide for workshop title
Titel_module	Title slide with module marker
Session	Slide to indicate the session
Topic	Slide to indicate in the topic of the current session
Standard	Regular slide to display your content
Exercise	Slide for exercises, similar to standard slide, just with a petrol frame as well as a link to the workshop pad.
Exercise_Menti	For exercises that use the tool Mentimeter. It is similar to the exercise slide, but includes a QR-Code to Mentimeter as well as the link and access code.
Break slide	There are three slides to use for breaks.
Lunch	There is one slide to use for lunch break.
Questions	There are three Q&A slides you can use during the Q&A session.
Evaluation	There is one slide you can use for evaluation of the workshop.

Colour scheme

The colour scheme is based on the NFDI4Chem colours. The colours are used as the following:

White: Background colour, text colour in boxes with a different background colour (e.g. NFDI4Chem petrol), HEX #FFFFFF

Black: Text colour, HEX #000000

NFDI4Chem petrol: Headline colour, first highlight colour, first box background colour, HEX #009CBC

Contrast colour orange: Second highlight colour, second box background colour, HEX #EE7400

Signal colour yellow: Highlight missing local input, last highlight colour, HEX #F1DE1E

Secondary violet: Colour for links, if necessary, also highlight colour, HEX #95569E

Secondary red: Optional highlight colour, mainly used for group work design, HEX #E30613

Secondary blue: Optional highlight colour, mainly used for group work design, HEX #0072B6

¹¹ e.g. at <https://fonts.adobe.com/fonts/ibm-plex-sans>.

Mainly stick to **NFDI4Chem petrol** and **contrast colour orange** if possible.

Illustrations

The training material contains illustrations by Katerina Limpitsouni (unDraw, <https://undraw.co/>). These illustrations can be used free of charge in this context without attribution and can be customised in colour. All of the illustrations here have been customised using the primary colour of NFDI4Chem petrol (HEX #009CBC). For more information, please refer to the licence: <https://undraw.co/license>.

Speaker notes

Speaker notes are provided for each slide. The notes are available in the PowerPoint files and as PDF files in the folder 03_Speaker-notes. These are divided into two parts: 'Notes' and 'Further information'.

The 'Notes' section provides guidance on the most important speaking points of each slide. Text in italics is intended to be read out loud, while non-italic text provides instructions or additional information. Please feel free to adapt and change them to suit your workshop style.

The 'Further Information' section is there if you want to know more about a topic. You will often find additional links and/or explanations there.

Workshop pad

We recommend to collect all links, references and further information relating to the workshop in a shared workshop pad (e.g. HedgeDoc) and make it available to participants. A short link to the workshop pad may also be included in the exercise master slide.

This approach has proven particularly effective for online workshops, as it enables participants to easily access exercise links. If you are running an on-site workshop, however, you will need to consider an alternative approach. As part of the training material, we provide a workshop pad template in markdown format (Example_Workshop_pad.md).

Exercises

Each module includes a set of exercises designed to encourage active learning and discussion. The exercises are numbered. Feel free to select the exercise that works best for you or add new exercises. The naming convention for the exercises is:

- MXXEXX
- MXX – Module number, e.g. M01, M02, M03, ...
- EXX – Exercise number, e.g. E01, E02, E03, ...

The exercises are primarily optimised for online workshop formats, for example by making use of collaborative tools, shared document and breakout sessions.

Alternative approaches for on-site workshops are provided for each exercise. These alternatives demonstrate how activities can be adapted for face-to-face settings through group work, printed materials and moderated discussions. Educators are encouraged to

select the most suitable format for their workshop and adapt the exercises further to suit their specific context and audience.

Detailed descriptions of the exercises, including learning objectives, required materials, estimated time and suggested variations, can be found in the following file: Exercises.docx. Facilitators should refer to this file when planning the workshop, selecting and adapting exercises that align with their teaching goals.

Material folder

The material folder (03_Example-files) contains all additional material that is used for exercises (e.g. pad templates, worksheets, Miro files and example images of whiteboards and Mentimeter polls). Each file is named with the respective exercise number.

Collaboration with local institutions

In the slide decks, you will find placeholders for local or institutional input (e.g. when discussing storage solutions). It has proven useful for workshop participants if information about their local options is added directly to the slides and discussed in relation to the topic. Slides for local input are marked with a yellow sign bearing the words 'Add local input or local options'.

References

References are provided wherever content created by others is used. There are generally two types of reference:

- References to source information used for the content on the slide, marked with 'Source:'
- References for graphics, comics, pictures, schemas and snapshots, marked with 'Figure:'

To ensure consistency in citations, please refer to our style guide for references.

Information on sources:

Information on sources is given in the bottom left-hand corner of a slide and always starts with 'Source:', followed by a link to the source. There are two different possibilities here:

1. The source has a persistent identifier (e.g. a DOI): Only the identifier is given (as a link). In case of DOI, please include '<https://doi.org>' in the identifier. Example:

Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6783902>

2. The source is a web source (e.g. website): The full URL of the web source is given (as a link) followed by information about the time the source was accessed, in the style: ', accessed: YYYY-MM-DD'. Example:

Source:

https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/data_life_cycle/,
accessed: 2025-11-03

Information on figures:

Information on figures, graphics, comics or schemas is given directly below (or to the right) of the relevant figure. This information always starts with 'Figure:', followed by the name of the figure, the creator (with a link, if possible), the licence (with a link to the licence text) and the place of publication (with a link). If the figure has no persistent identifier, the access date is added in the same way as for the 'Source', in the format 'accessed: YYYY-MM-DD'. Provide as much of this information as possible. Example:

Figure: “Folder vs. Metadata” by [John Norris](#) licensed under [CC BY-SA 3.0](#) via [john-norris.net](#),
accessed: 2025-12-09